

1 **Supplementary material - Hindcast Simulation of Competing Water Uses in**
2 **Alpine Multi-reservoir Operations: The Orco System**

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8 **REFERENCES**

9 IREN S.p.A. (2022). “Technical documentation for the end of concession of the orco hydropower
10 system.” *technical report*, IREN S.p.A., Italy. Technical reports prepared for the concession
11 renewal process and submitted to the competent authority.

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14 are derived from observed relationships between storage conditions, inflow avail-
15 ability, and electricity prices. Environmental flow releases are always satisfied as a
16 binding constraint prior to turbine operation. 4

TABLE S1. Simplified heuristic operating rules for reservoir hydropower management. Rules are derived from observed relationships between storage conditions, inflow availability, and electricity prices. Environmental flow releases are always satisfied as a binding constraint prior to turbine operation.

Storage level	Storage trend	Dominant driver	Observed operating behaviour
Low	Decreasing	Water conservation / price	Reduced generation; limited response to price, with slight increase under favourable market conditions
Low	Stable or increasing	Inflow availability	Turbinning follows inflow: near-minimum generation under scarcity, run-of-river behaviour under high inflow
High	-	Price signal (moderate inflow)	Flexible operation; increased generation during high-price periods
High	-	Spill prevention (high inflow)	Sustained high generation to avoid spillage, largely independent of price

Note: Environmental flow requirements are enforced as a prior constraint in all operating conditions.

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